

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHEIKH****FIRST NAME: MAHDI Omar****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student used Turabian Style.

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

The author used the following software: (MS-Office Professional plus 2013)

QUIZ FOR ACA-401D COURSE

1. What's plagiarism?
 - When the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas.
 - It is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.
 - When the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information¹**
 - Method used to indicate where a piece of information came from.

2. State some rules of thumb for writing a paper?
 - Choose the Turabian Style for writing.
 - Choose the US English for writing.
 - State the main thesis of your paper at (or near) the beginning: preferably in the opening paragraph.²**
 - Flow the Euclid template for the response paper.

3. What is ethnography in the research?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

² Ibid., 12.

- a systematic, collaborative, and democratic orientation toward inquiry that seeks effective solutions to complex problems that people confront in their communities and organizations
 - A form of qualitative research focused on discovering and describing the culture of a group of people and learning what it is like to be a member of the group from the perspectives of the members themselves.**³
 - Assumes society is structured by class, status, race, ethnicity, gender, and sexual orientation in order to maintain the oppression of marginalized groups.
 - Focuses on how individuals assign meaning to their experiences through the stories they tell.
4. What is the transferability of the research?
- It is concerned with establishing that the researcher's findings and interpretations are clearly derived from the data, requiring the researcher to demonstrate how conclusions have been reached.
 - The researcher must ensure that the research process is clearly documented, logical, and traceable. It refers to the stability and consistency of data over time.
 - Refers to whether the participants' perceptions match up with the researcher's portrayal of them.
 - Refers to the fit or match between the research context and other contexts as judged by the reader.**⁴
5. What to note when you are handing in an essay?
- Start writing early - the earlier, the better.
 - Make sure you know the date the assignment is due because submitting late work usually incurs a late penalty.**⁵
 - Always keep the topic or question of the essay clearly in mind.
 - Define the question and analyze the task and present the answers to the question.
6. One of the reasons for citing your sources is:
- To develop effective writing habits.
 - To make the subjects short and concrete.
 - To give credit**⁶.

³ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Columbia University, 2019), 164.

⁴ Ibid., 477.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course-pack, Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 12.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2019), 139.

- To make readers understand the importance of the research.
7. In the Turabian style, For references to times of day in even increments of an hour, half hour, or quarter hour,
- Spell out the times, with a hyphen between parts**⁷
 - Form the plurals of spelled-out numbers like the plurals of other nouns.
 - You may group smaller tables or figures on a page, as long as they are clearly distinct from one another.
 - If the figure is a photograph or other image, consider reducing it.
8. How to cite articles in magazines compared to journal articles (Using Turabian)?
- Reference list entries include volume number, issue number, and month or season.
 - The volume number follows the journal title without intervening punctuation and is not italicized.
 - If you add an English translation, enclose it in brackets, without quotation marks
 - Articles in magazines are cited much like journal articles, but dates and page numbers are treated differently**⁸.
9. How to cite unpublished interview (using Turabian)?
- It should normally be cited only in the text.
 - To cite an unpublished interview (including one you have conducted yourself), begin a reference list entry with the name of the person interviewed, followed by the date and the name of the interviewer.**⁹
 - It should include in the reference list entry a URL.
 - Use *forthcoming* in place of the date (and page numbers).
10. What's Post-positivism in qualitative research?
- Knowledge claims arise out of situations, actions, and consequences rather than from antecedent conditions.
 - The basic tenet of post-positivism is that reality is socially, culturally, and historically constructed.
 - It has a clear focus on social justice and includes feminist perspectives, racialized discourses, and disability inquiry.

⁷ Ibid., 344.

⁸ Ibid., 266.

⁹ Ibid., 273.

- It refers to a school of thought that maintains that all knowledge can be derived from direct observation and logical inferences based on that observation.¹⁰

¹⁰ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Loss Angeles: Columbia University, 2019), 147.

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